

CHEMISTRY

HYDROGENATION OF ALLYL ALCOHOL USING A POLYMER-SUPPORTED NICKEL-BASED CATALYST

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Abstract

Allyl alcohol is an oxygen-containing organic compound and the first representative of the class of unsaturated alcohols. It is an industrially significant olefinic alcohol, widely used as a precursor for various chemical compounds. The hydrogenation product of allyl alcohol, 1-propanol, is a versatile solvent and chemical intermediate employed in multiple industrial sectors. Given its broad applicability, the hydrogenation of allyl alcohol is of considerable scientific and industrial interest. Notably, metallic nickel is used as an active phase in hydrogenation reactions due to its accessibility and electronic structure, which is similar to that of precious metal catalysts. In the present study, highly efficient nanocatalysts containing different weight percentages of Ni were synthesized on a synthetic polymer matrix, poly(4-vinylpyridine) (P4VP), for the selective hydrogenation of allyl alcohol to 1-propanol. The hydrogenation process was conducted at temperatures ranging from 40°C to 80°C under atmospheric pressure.

The findings indicate that the catalytic activity of the synthesized catalyst samples in the investigated reaction is significantly influenced by the nature, properties, and structure of both the polymer and the metal, as well as the reaction conditions, particularly the temperature.

Keywords: allyl alcohol, hydrogenation reaction, 1-propanol, nanocatalysts, P4VP/Ni complex.

Introduction

Hydrogenation reactions play a crucial role in biotechnological processing plants, as well as in the production of essential products for the fragrance, food seasoning, and pharmaceutical industries. These products are obtained by reducing the O/H ratio of biomaterials with high oxygen content [1].

In this context, the hydrogenation of allyl alcohol is particularly relevant. Various Pd and Pt nanoparticles (NPs) have been synthesized and tested as catalysts for the hydrogenation of allyl alcohols, starting from suitable metal ions and lignosulfonates. In this process, Pt NPs predominantly produce saturated alcohols, whereas Pd NPs exhibit high activity, leading not only to the formation of saturated alcohols but also to the production of unsaturated isomeric alcohols and aldehydes. Additionally, these catalysts have demonstrated low selectivity [2].

In this study, a series of γ,γ -disubstituted and β,γ -disubstituted allylic alcohols were synthesized and efficiently hydrogenated using appropriate N,P-based Ir complexes. Most of the substrates exhibited high yields and excellent enantioselectivities. Additionally, the investigation highlighted the influence of the acidity of N, P-Ir complexes on acid-sensitive allylic alcohols. To elucidate the effect of the N, P-ligand on the acidity of the corresponding Ir-complex, DFT ΔpK_a calculations were performed. Furthermore, the reaction's selectivity model enabled an accurate prediction of the absolute configuration of the hydrogenated alcohols [3].

Rh complexes generally result in high enantiomeric excesses (ee's) in the asymmetric hydrogenation of allylic alcohols that possess at least one aryl group at the γ -carbon [4]. When Rh complexes are used as cata-

lysts, high catalyst loadings and often prolonged reaction times are required. Despite the high enantioselectivity achieved with Ru catalysts, the reaction scope remains relatively limited, particularly for substrates containing aliphatic substituents.

High diastereoselective hydrogenation of allylic alcohols has also been achieved using N-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs) and N-based Ir complexes [5]. However, only a few Ir-based catalysts have been shown to provide high enantioselectivity in asymmetric hydrogenation [6], and the reduction process often leads to complex product mixtures. Notably, C=C isomerization is frequently observed as a competing process during hydrogenation with Rh, Ru, and Ir complexes, especially under low-pressure conditions [7].

Allylic alcohols can be considered relatively acid-sensitive compounds. Protonation of the hydroxyl group, followed by the elimination of water, leads to the formation of allylic carbocations. It was hypothesized that the formation of carbocationic intermediates contributes to the complex mixture of reaction products observed in certain hydrogenation processes. A series of allylic alcohols capable of generating different types of carbocations were tested in hydrogenation reactions using various catalysts based on different heterocycles [3].

Materials and Methods

Allyl alcohol, the first representative of the class of unsaturated alcohols, is an oxygen-containing organic compound. It is a colorless liquid with a sharp, mustard-like odor. It is soluble in water and many organic solvents, forming an azeotropic mixture with water (28.3% H₂O) in all proportions. Its chemical structure is CH₂=CH-CH₂OH, with a molecular weight of 58.1 g/mol, a melting point of -129°C, and a boiling point of 97°C.

Despite environmental concerns, allyl alcohol remains an important organic intermediate in the synthesis of polymer compounds produced industrially from petroleum-derived propylene. It is an industrially significant olefinic alcohol that serves as a raw material or precursor for many chemical compounds. When treated with concentrated HCl at 100°C in the presence of ZnCl₂ or at 200°C in the presence of CuCl₂, allyl alcohol is converted into allyl chloride. Passing it over Al₂O₃ at 200–300°C leads to the formation of diallyl ether. Allyl alcohol readily forms both simple and complex ethers. Its conversion to acrolein is catalyzed by alcohol dehydrogenase.

Allyl alcohol is used in optical resins, protective glass, paints and coatings, silane coupling agents, and polymer cross-linking agents. Additionally, it is widely employed in the production of pharmaceuticals, organic chemicals, plastics, herbicides, and pesticides [8–12].

In this study, allyl alcohol with a purity of 99%, supplied by the “Vekton” ZAO company, was used. It is a highly flammable liquid with the molecular formula C₃H₅OH. Allyl alcohol has a molecular weight of 58.08 g/mol, a boiling point of 97°C, and a density of 0.85 g/cm³. It is miscible with water and most organic solvents.

The synthetic polymer poly(4-vinylpyridine) was obtained using 4-vinylpyridine from the “Merck” company through multiple vacuum distillations in the presence of the radical inhibitor hydroquinone. The fraction collected for the experiment was stored in a black glass container at temperatures above 50°C, under a helium atmosphere, and in the presence of hydroquinone. The polymer retains a moisture content of 5–6% at most and a minimum of 0.5%. It is highly soluble in many organic solvents but has very limited solubility in water.

Ethanol is a transparent, colorless liquid with a characteristic pleasant odor. It has a high flammability and is commonly used as a solvent for various chemical compounds. As a volatile organic compound, ethanol readily mixes with water and many organic liquids.

1-Propanol is a colorless, flammable liquid with the chemical formula C₃H₈O. It has a molecular weight of approximately 60.1 g/mol, a boiling point of around 97.2°C, and a density of 0.803 g/cm³. It is miscible with water, ethanol, and other organic solvents.

Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O – Nickel(II) nitrate hexahydrate has a molecular weight of 182.7 g/mol and is green in color.

The separation of reaction products was carried out using an Agilent 7890B gas chromatograph. The analysis was performed with an HP-5 column, with a carrier gas (H₂) flow rate of 1.2 mL/min. Reaction products were injected into the chromatograph every 60 minutes using a syringe.

Result and Discussion

Given the high cost of platinum-group elements, the development of more economically viable catalysts is of significant importance. In this context, nickel-based catalysts have garnered increased interest due to their high activity in hydrogenation reactions compared to other catalysts.

The scientific novelty of this research lies in the development of an economically efficient nickel-based nanocatalyst system as an alternative to platinum-group elements and in demonstrating its high potential in hydrogenation reactions. This study represents a significant step toward the creation of a novel, efficient, and cost-effective nanocatalyst system for the selective hydrogenation of allyl alcohol to 1-propanol.

One of the promising directions in this field is the design of catalysts obtained by immobilizing metal complexes onto polymer supports.

Nanotechnology is recognized as an emerging field of modern science that utilizes nanoscale systems. It encompasses the synthesis, manipulation, and application of materials ranging from below the micrometer scale down to individual atoms. Nanoparticles serve as the fundamental building blocks of nanotechnology [13].

Nanocatalysis is a rapidly evolving field with growing significance in modern catalysis. It is primarily considered an intermediate domain between homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis, as synthesized nanocatalysts can be employed in both catalytic processes. Nanocatalysis has emerged from the direct connection between homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis, bringing unique solutions for optimizing catalyst properties. Several characteristics of nanocatalysts

are under investigation, including high efficiency, selectivity, stability, ease of regeneration, and recyclability [14,15].

The essential characteristics of a catalyst required for the hydrogenation of allyl alcohol include high activity, selectivity, stability, and resistance to coking. Among the various metal-based catalysts used for this reaction, nickel-modified catalysts have been more extensively studied due to their high activity in hydrogenation reactions and, most notably, their economic advantage of being relatively inexpensive compared to other catalysts.

Considering this, nickel-containing nanocatalysts in a polymer matrix were synthesized and their physicochemical and catalytic properties were investigated in the hydrogenation reaction of allyl alcohol to propyl alcohol (1-propanol).

It is important to note that the hydrogenation of allyl alcohol results in the formation of the saturated alcohol 1-propanol ($\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$). During the reaction, the unsaturated $\text{C}=\text{C}$ double bond in allyl alcohol undergoes hydrogenation, leading to the formation of a fully saturated alcohol. The reaction equation is as follows:

$$\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2\text{OH} + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \text{ (in the presence of a catalyst)}$$

If selective hydrogenation occurs, only the double bond may undergo hydrogenation, leading to the formation of propenol ($\text{CH}_3-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$). However, this compound is rarely stable, and 1-propanol is predominantly obtained.

For this purpose, nickel/poly-4-vinylpyridine-based complexes with different weight percentages of nickel (5%, 10%, 15%) were synthesized using an established methodology [16]. These complexes were then tested in the hydrogenation of allyl alcohol. The hydrogenation reaction was conducted at temperatures ranging from 40°C to 80°C under atmospheric pressure.

The conducted studies have determined that the catalytic activity of the synthesized catalyst samples in the investigated reaction is significantly dependent on the nature, properties, and structure of the polymer and metal, as well as the reaction conditions, including temperature and other factors. As a result the optimal metal content in the catalyst (10 wt.%) and the optimal reaction conditions ($T = 60^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}:\text{H}_2 = 1:3$) were determined, yielding a 1-propanol output of 27.3 wt.% with a conversion rate of 43.5 wt.%.

Conclusion

Thus, as a result of the conducted research, effective nanocatalysts containing various weight percentages of Ni were synthesized on the synthetic polymer poly-4-vinylpyridine for the selective hydrogenation of allyl alcohol to propanol-1. The optimal metal content in the catalyst (10 wt.%) and the optimal reaction conditions ($T=60^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}:\text{H}_2=1:3$) were determined, yielding a propanol-1 output of 27.3 wt.% with a conversion of 43.5 wt.%.

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